

FORMULATION OF HERBAL VANISHING CREAM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present research work was to formulate and evaluate vanishing herbal cream. Herbal creams offer several advantages over other creams. The majority of existing creams which has prepared from drugs of synthetic origin and give extras fairness to face, but it has several side effects such as itching or several allergic reactions. Herbal creams do not have any of these side effects, without side effects it gives the fairness look to skin. Herbs are used in vanishing cream using aloe-vera. Synthetic compounds such as stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, isopropyl, potassium hydroxide, preservative and perfume are used in formulation of vanishing cream. The physical parameters such as pH, homogeneity by visual and by touch, appearance, wash ability, consistency, Patch test, irritancy test determined.

KEYWORDS: Herbal extracts, Vanishing cream, Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Creams are semisolid emulsions intended for application to the skin or mucous membrane. A low-fat moisturizer that disappears into the skin is called as a vanishing cream. It softens skin, leaving nothing behind. Vanishing cream are o/w emulsion-based preparations containing aqueous phase and oil phase.

Herbs such as aloe-vera. Synthetic compounds such as stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, isopropyl, potassium hydroxide, preservative and perfume are used in formulation of vanishing cream.

It can be used as primer before make up due to its vanishing property. They are used to hold power on the skin as well as to improve adhesion. This cream is used in hot climate that help in perspiration on the skin. It can also be used as foundation cream.

These creams provide emollient as well as protective action to the skin against the environmental conditions by forming a semi occlusive residual-film. This film is

neither greasy nor oily. As vanishing creams were non-greasy, they were suitable on persons with oily skin.

Vanishing cream is a cosmetic product, typically an oil-in-water emulsion, named for its property of being absorbed into the skin without leaving a greasy residue, often used as a base for makeup or as a cleansing and moisturizing cream.

KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF VANISHING CREAM

Formulation: It is an oil-in-water emulsion, meaning it contains a higher percentage of water compared to oil.
Key Ingredients: Stearic acid is a primary component, along with emulsifiers to create the emulsion, and often includes glycerine for its humectant properties and to prevent drying out, and preservatives for microbial stability.
Application and Effect: When applied to the skin, the continuous water phase of the emulsion evaporates, leaving behind a thin, non-greasy film of the stearic acid, which helps to soften and protect the skin.
Uses: It can be used as a base for makeup, as a

moisturizing or cleansing cream, or even mixed with liquid foundation to create a custom tinted moisturizer.

IDEAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VANISHING CREAM

1. It should have high melting point.
2. It should be pure white in colour.
3. It should possess a very slight odour.
4. Rubbed easily on the skin.
5. The vanishing cream pH should ideally range from 4.6 to 6.0.

ADVANTAGES

- It helps to keep the skin moisturized. In dry and cold areas, a lot of people use vanishing creams to keep their skin from becoming rough and scaly.
- Softens the skin and provides a shiny texture to the skin.
- Prevents skin roughening.
- A great benefit of using vanishing creams is that it does not stick or annoy the skin.
- Vanishing cream are also helpful in keeping the skin afresh.
- Vanishing creams retain the moisture and this helps in keeping the skin healthy.
- It is sometimes used as the base for cosmetics and make-up and even just plain foundation.
- It is easier for the pores to be blocked.

APPLICATIONS

1. **Sheen effect:** One characteristic due to which these vanishing creams are preferred is the sheen effect. Rather than giving a caked look to the face, they give a natural attractive sheen to the skin.
2. **Daily day creams:** Vanishing cream has the advantages of bring non greasy which makes them suitable for the use during the day and by women with oily skin. In addition to keeping powder on the face, they also protect the skin from the elements such as chapping winds and dry breezes.
3. **Moisture locking power:** The magical quality of vanishing cream that makes it is a choice as daily cream is the moisture locking power. As many women know that moisture is the key element of healthy skin, the mystical power of vanishing cream still eludes some women. It is equally effective for normal and oily skin types.
4. **Lightens age spot:** One important constituent of the cream is hydroquinone. This chemical is well known in dispelling shallowness and freckles. Four percent hydroquinone applied consistency is supposed to vanish all the ages spots. The purpose of the vanishing cream is to lighten unnecessary dark spots or discolorations on the skin.

OBJECTIVES OF HERBAL VANISHING CREAM

1. **Moisturizing**– To provide light hydration to the skin without leaving it greasy.

2. **Matte Finish**– To reduce excess oil and shine on the face, giving a smooth, non-greasy appearance.
3. **Skin Protection**– To form a thin protective layer against dust, dirt, and environmental pollutants.
4. **Even Skin Tone**– To improve complexion and help in reducing the appearance of blemishes or uneven skin tone.
5. **Base for Makeup**– To act as a primer or base before applying makeup, ensuring smoother application.
6. **Cooling Effect**– To give a refreshing and soothing feel to the skin.
7. **Affordable Daily Care**– To serve as an economical, everyday skincare product suitable for all skin types, especially oily and combination skin.

METHODOLOGY

- **PRE-FORMULATION** Steps involved in extraction of aloe vera
 1. Removal of yellow substance from aloe Vera leaf.
 2. Extraction of aloe vera pulp from leaf. Preparation of herbal vanishing cream containing from aloe vera extraction

EVALUATION PARAMETERS OF THE HERBAL VANISHING CREAM

- Time of Disappearance.
- pH Determination test.
- Dilution test.
- Spread ability test.
- Washability test.

INGREDIENTS (MATERIALS) USED IN FORMULATION

In formulation of vanishing cream, lots of materials (ingredients) used.

ALOEVERA: It stimulates fibroblast which produces the collagen and collagen leaps to skin hydration. Mono co-polysaccharides helps in binding moisture into the skin.

Biological Source: Aloe is obtained from the dried juice of leaves of *Aloe Barbadensis Miller*.

Family: Liliaceae.

Chemical Constituents: It contains anthracene glycosides, cinnamic acid, coumaric acid, and vitamins A, B and C.

Uses: □□ It is used to treat skin problems. □□ It is used as anti-bacterial and anti-inflammatory agent. □□ It is used for hydrating the skin. □□ It is used for softening of the skin.

INGREDIENTS

Table 1: Formulation Table INGREDIENTS QUANTITY FOR 100 GM.

INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY FOR 100 GM
Aloevera Extract	3.5 gm
Stearic acid	15 gm
Catyl alcohol	0.50 gm
Sodium carbonate	0.5 gm
Potassium hydroxide	0.50 gm
glycerine	6 gm
Methyl paraben	0.5 gm
Water	72.5 gm
Rose water	1 gm

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF HERBAL VANISHING CREAM

- **Preparation of Extract: Preparation of Fresh Aloevera Leaf Extract**
- **Material required:** Fresh Aloevera leaves Distilled water / ethanol (depending on extraction type) Knife, blender/mixer, muslin cloth or filter paper, beaker
- **Steps for Extraction:**
 - 1. Collection of leaves:** Select thick, healthy, mature Aloe vera leaves (outer leaves).
 - 2. Cleaning:** Wash thoroughly with distilled water to remove dirt and debris.
 - 3. Peeling:** Remove the outer green rind with a clean knife.
 - Collect the inner mucilaginous gel.**
 - 4. Grinding:** Cut the gel into small pieces and grind in a blender to obtain a homogenous extract.
 - 5. Filtration:** Filter the slurry through muslin cloth or Whatman filter paper to remove fibers.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS FOR HERBAL VANISHING CREAM

- 1. Determination of Organoleptic Characteristics:** The appearance of the cream was judged by its color, pearlescence and roughness and graded.
- 2. PH Test:** The pH of vanishing cream was determined using pH meter. The most accurate common means of measuring pH is through a lab device called a probe and meter, or simply a pH meter. The probe consists of a glass electrode through which a small voltage is passed. The meter is a voltmeter, measures the electronic impedance in the glass electrode and displays pH units instead of volts. Measurement is made by submerging the probe in the semisolid until a reading is registered by the meter.
- 3. Dilution Test:** In this test, the herbal vanishing cream was diluted either with oil or water. If the emulsion is o/w type and it is diluted with water, it will remain stable as a water dispersion medium but if it is diluted with oil, the emulsion will break as oil and water are not miscible with each other. Oil in water emulsion can easily be diluted with an aqueous solvent, where water in oil emulsion can be diluted with an oily liquid.

Fig. 1: Dilution test.

4. Determination of homogeneity

The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch.

5. Spread ability test

The spread ability of herbal vanishing cream was determined by placing 0.5gm cream within a circle of 1cm diameter pre marked on a glass plate over which a second glass plate was placed. A weight of 500gm was allowed to rest on the upper glass plate for 5min. spread ability refers to the area covered by a fixed amount of cream sample after the uniform spread of sample on the glass slide. The increase in the diameter due to spreading of the cream was noted. Average of three determinations was noted.

- 6. Patch Test:** About 1-3gm of material to be tested was placed on a piece of fabric or funnel and applied to the sensitive part of the skin e.g. skin behind ears. The cosmetic to be tested was applied to an area of 1sq.m. of the skin. Control patches (of similar cosmetic of known brand) were also applied. The

site of patch is inspected after 24 hrs. As there was no reaction the test was repeated three times. As no reaction was observed on third application, the person may be taken as not hypersensitive.

7. **Appearance:** The appearance of the cream was found by observing its color, opacity, etc.
8. **Smear type:** The test was conducted after the application of cream on the skin the smear formed was oily or aqueous in nature.
9. **Determination of emolliency:** Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amounts of cream was checked.

10. Wash ability: The removal of the cream applied on skin was done by washing under tap water with minimal force to remove the cream.

11. Irritancy test: The cream was applied on left hand dorsal side surface of 1sq.cm and observed in equal intervals up to 24hrs for irritancy, redness and edema.

12. Accelerated stability studies: Accelerated stability studies were performed on all the formulations by maintaining at room temperature for 20 days with constant time interval. During the stability studies the parameters like homogeneity, viscosity, physical changes, pH and type of smear were studied.

Table 2: Evaluation parameter.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Appearance	White
2	Odor	Slightly aromatic
3	pH	5.19
4	Spreadability	Uniform with a value of 42 g.cm/sec Easily spreadable
5	Dye Test with Scarlet red	O/W type
6	Homogeneity By visual By Touch	Homogenous Smooth and Consistent
7	Patch Test	Not hypersensitiveness
8	Type of Smear	Non-greasy
9	Emolliency	No residue left
10	Consistency	Good
11	Washability	Washable
12	Irritancy test	No redness and edema
13	Accelerated stability study	Stable
14	Grittiness	No gritty particles

RESULTS

Table 3: Evaluation Parameters for Herbal Vanishing Cream Formulations.

Sr.no	Parameters	F1	F2	F3
1.	Color	White	White	Yellow
2.	Odor	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3.	Time of Disappearance	Rapidly	Rapidly	Rapidly
4.	pH Determination	5.19	4.8	3.9
5.	Dilution test	O/W	O/W	O/W
6.	Spreadability (cm)	4cm	3.8cm	4cm
7.	Washability	Washable	Washable	Washable
8.	Homogeneity	Homogenous, smooth & consistent	Homogenous, smooth & consistent	Homogenous, smooth & consistent

F1 – Formulation containing 3.5 ml of aloe vera extract.

F2 – Formulation containing 3 ml of aloe vera extract.

F3 – Formulation containing 5 ml of aloe vera extract.

DISCUSSION

Herbal vanishing cream made from aloe vera herbs is a natural and effective skincare product that offers numerous benefits for the skin. Each of these herbs has unique properties that can help to nourish, hydrate, and rejuvenate the skin for a healthy and radiant complexion. Aloe vera is a versatile herb that is widely used in

skincare products for its healing and moisturizing properties. It has anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties that can help to soothe irritated skin, heal wounds, and prevent breakouts. Aloe vera also contains vitamins and minerals that can nourish and hydrate the skin for a healthy glow. Overall, herbal vanishing cream made from, and aloe vera herbs is a fantastic choice for anyone looking to improve the health and appearance of their skin naturally. It can be used daily as part of a skincare routine to keep the skin looking and feeling its best.

CONCLUSION

The vanishing cream of herbs with the best properties and having nutritional value was to be prepared by simple methods and less equipment are required. The prepared herbal cream also has antioxidant and antibacterial activity due to this it retards aging signs and pimple formation on the face. Further studies are required for this vanishing herbal cream. It was found that this type of formulation of the vanishing herbal cream was not prepared earlier. Oil in water emulsion-based cream was formulated using natural ingredients and was evaluated. By combining aloe vera with synthetic ingredients it can be concluded that this cream can be used as a multipurpose cream and the ingredients mixed can produce synergistic effect of the other. Further studies can be carried out on stability and skin irritancy test of the cream. **Based on the above studies, following conclusion can be drawn.** □ The prepared formulations showed good physical characteristics. □ The pH of the formulations were found to be 5.19 □ The spread ability of formulation were found to be 4 Among the three formulations the formulation F1 was found to be promising had shown good results compared with F2 herbal vanishing cream. F3 has not shown our expected results. The promising formulations have displayed good pH determination, spread ability and antimicrobial activity which indicates better and faster absorption into the skin. From the above studies it can be concluded that herbal vanishing cream are stable and safe without side effects. This study can be helpful for upcoming research to select the herbs for the formulation and evaluation of other cosmetic applications which can be claimed for their efficacy.

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